

The significance of resilience based approach regarding the tackling of human trafficking | Krisztina Kállai

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Abstract

The challenge of human trafficking concerning children from the region of devastated areas caused by natural disasters is an increasingly significant fact. As the sudden natural disasters are more erratic, the number of exploited minor victims will be growing significantly. Having no parental authority most of these minors become victims of sexual exploitation. Applying an adequate resilience based approach included the psychosocial support could be a major tool of process of both prevention and rehabilitation among the sexually exploited children.

Introduction

As the climate change is accelerating, the effects of it is conspicuous globally, affecting all the parts of our life. Firstly, this dynamic will generate much higher energy and food prices. Floods, hurricanes, droughts are already driving a dangerous spike in food prices, and the effects of climate change will continue to worsen. Therefore climate refugees flows toward the US, Europe, in the hope of better life who will be the main target of human traffickers.

Due to the complex nature of the phenomenon of trafficking of human beings, it is much more than the organized transportation of persons for financial gain, in this sense, it is distinguished from the smuggling of migrants by the fact that a critical factor is present in the latter case: the violence or deception that characterizes the whole process. Incomplete identification of victims of trafficking may lead to further violations for those individuals. Human rights violations are both causes and consequences of human trafficking. Accordingly, it is essential that measures to prevent and stop trafficking of human beings focus on the protection of human rights. Victims of trafficking of human beings, as victims of human rights violations, are guaranteed the right to an adequate and satisfactory remedy under international law. Victims of human trafficking are often unable to exercise these rights, as in many cases they are not properly informed about the remedies and procedures available for trafficking in human beings and related exploitation. To address this problem, legal and other financial assistance should be provided to victims of human trafficking in the affected areas in order to enable them to exercise their right to an adequate and satisfactory remedy. As regards minor victims of trafficking of human beings, the high degree of physical, mental and psychosocial trauma resulting from exploitation, as well as their

increased vulnerability to exploitation, necessitate that this group be treated separately from adult victims by law and anti-trafficking programs. The best interests of the child shall be a primary consideration in all actions concerning minor victims of trafficking in human beings, regardless of whether both preventive and rehabilitative action is taken by public or private social welfare institutions.

The features and practical methods of resilience

Resilience is a flexible ability of resistance, it means the ability of a system, be it an individual, an organization, an ecosystem, to successfully adapt to strong, renewable, or even shock-like external influences. Back in the 1970s, Holling, a leading figure in resilience research, pointed out the paradox between a system's performance, carrying capacity and ability to survive and change. There are two different definitions of resilience. According to the first definition, resilience is the range of measures within which a system maintains its internal balance against applied forces. In the second definition, the concept of stability is reinterpreted, the system reacts to the force that tipped it from its previous equilibrium state in such a way as to obtain a new equilibrium in a flexible way (1973, Holling, pp. 1-23).

In the wording of Garnezy, Masten, Tellegen (1984, pp. 97-111), resilience is a manifestation of a child's competence against the stressful events that affect him or her. According to Rutter (2007, pp. 205-209) facing stress allows for an increase in self-confidence and competence. Rutter argues that resilience cannot be interpreted as a personality trait, as one may be resilient to one type of challenge while not to another. Resilience can rather be interpreted as a dynamic process, one has to consider interactions with environment in addition to internal capabilities. Resilience refers to the process by which an individual shows positive adaptation despite unfavorable, threatening conditions.

Numerous theories and studies describe the concept of resilience in relation to trauma, but no uniform definition has been developed to date. There are currently two approaches: one for Bonanno, which is a narrower definition, and the other is a broader one. Bonanno (Bonanno et al., 2009, pp. 1150–1164) considers the effects of a single, short-term trauma. Some researchers cite sources within individuals, while others believe that resilience may develop from different sources and not only from those within the individuals. Thus, even psychological and dispositional characteristics as well as the social context (e.g. family and other external support network) should be taken into account. In general, each approach associates the notion of resilience with other similar and overlapping constructs, such as "hardiness," "thriving," and "posttraumatic growth". In resilient individuals, positive emotions are effective in reducing stressful experiences and helping to activate psychological resources in both general and

shocking disaster situations. Resistant people experience several positive emotions, the importance of which is supported by the experience gained in rehabilitation and recovery from diseases.

Overall, all definitions of resilience suggest that the hardiness individual is more confident, has a more efficient repository of coping skills, and is able to take advantage of social support. Furthermore, resilience is a complex construct, so its definition may be different at the level of the individual, family, organization, society, or even culture (Fredrickson et al., 2003, pp. 365–376).

One of the best-known programs at the individual and school level is BoingBoing in the UK, which operates within the YoungMinds voluntary aid organization. YoungMinds is a preventive initiative aimed at ensuring the emotional well-being of British children and adolescents, preserving their mental health and, where necessary, recognizing and treating mental illness in a time (Hart and Heaver, 2015). BoingBoing is targeted at disadvantaged students that is different from the majority of society. The program aims to develop subjective well-being and resilience by offering a theoretical framework and developed methods involving five main areas (basic needs, belonging, learning, coping and self-knowledge). The program also implicitly includes the development of Academic Resilience Approach (AGA), for which a free student workbook is available. Another similar initiative is the United Kingdom Resilience Program (UKRP), a British adaptation of the Penn Resilience Program (Gillham et al., 2007, pp. 9–19). This program does not directly develop resilience, but provides general skills development during interventions that can help overcome school difficulties at several points. The 18-occupational framework program, designed for the primary school age group, focuses primarily on the development of emotional intelligence, problem-solving thinking, self-efficacy, and social competencies. The effectiveness of the program was clearly demonstrated by reducing the symptoms of depression, however, behavioural problems and anxiety symptoms did not show a significant change after the program. The theories do not contradict each other, but show a number of construction overlaps. Resilience is difficult to separate from the more general notion of coping, the theoretical boundary between the two phenomena is less obvious. The question arises as to whether resilience, and within this, academic resilience, is indeed an independent phenomenon or rather a part, a result, a manifestation of successful coping mechanisms or psychological immune competence. The right of exist of the concept of academic resilience is also supported by the fact that schools have a fundamental role in eliminating social disadvantages and creating equal opportunities. In this sense, it is important to interpret academic resilience as an independent phenomenon, as development plans and goals can be formulated and implemented along measurable achievements in a well-defined social context, based on this

concept. Especially when we consider a systems-based approach to resilience, that is, we focus not only on developing students' resilience-supporting qualities, but also on ensuring that these students receive support for development in an appropriate school environment (Challen et al., 2014, pp. 75–89).

The aim is for their development potential to be truly realized and for the interaction with the environment to create the support that makes them successful, but at least protects them from drifting to the margins and reproducing their social disadvantages. In this sense, we can also speak of a resilient student and a school supporting resilience, in which the two concepts are dynamically linked, thereby strengthening or weakening each other's impact. In an even broader sense, the school operates embedded in a social environment, so the phenomenon of institutional and social resilience can also be examined.

Conclusion

In many cases, the current programs have general objectives and the criteria for inclusion in the program are not sufficiently precise. Thus, it is sometimes not clear whether this is a preventive or interventional method, and the two levels are blurred in many cases. Many prevention and intervention programs state the development of resilience as declared goals, but the focus of practices and procedures is to increase "well-being" in a more general sense or to develop life skills. One of the most critical points in the application of prevention and intervention programs is the measurement of effectiveness, which is rarely the case for interventions to develop resilience, largely due to the uncertain definition of resilience. However, the study of the effects is complicated by the fact that the measurement methodology is basically based on a quantitative technique. A more precise exploration of the phenomenon would require the involvement of qualitative (interview, semi-projective, projective) procedures, both in the research clarifying the mechanisms and in the impact assessment of the programs. Furthermore adequate assistance and protection should be provided to minor victims of trafficking of human beings and their special rights and needs should be fully taken into account. The development and application of resilience-based methods can be used to meet these needs and requirements, which can significantly contribute to the implementation of effective action against trafficking of human beings, keeping in mind the fundamental human rights and the protection of victims.

References

- Bonanno, G. A., Wortman, C. B., Lehman, D. R., Tweed, R. G., Haring, M., Sonnega, J., Nesse, R. M. (2002). Resilience to loss and chronic grief: A prospective study from preloss to 18-months postloss. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*. pp. 1150–1164. <https://doi.apa.org/doiLanding?doi=10.1037%2F0022-3514.83.5.1150> (Accessed: December, 2021)
- Challen, A. R., Machin, S. J., & Gillham, J. E. (2014). The UK Resilience Programme: A schoolbased universal nonrandomized pragmatic controlled trial. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, pp. 75–89. <https://doi.apa.org/doiLanding?doi=10.1037%2Fa0034854> (Accessed: December, 2021)
- C. S. Holling (1973). RESILIENCE AND STABILITY OF ECOLOGICAL SYSTEMS. Resilience and Stability of Ecological Systems Author(s): C. S. Holling Reviewed works. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*, Vol. 4. pp. 1-23. https://www.zoology.ubc.ca/bdg/pdfs_bdg/2013/Holling%201973.pdf (Accessed: December, 2021)
- Fredrickson, B. L., Tugade, M. M., Waugh, C. E., Larkin, G. R. (2003). What good are positive emotions in crisis? A prospective study of resilience and emotions following the terrorist attacks on the United States on September 11th, 2001. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, pp. 365–376. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2003-01140-011> (Accessed: December, 2021)
- Garmezy, N., Masten, A. S., Tellegen, A. (1984). The study of stress and Competenx in children: A building block for developmental psycho pathology. *Child Development*, pp. 97-111.
- Gillham, J. E., Reivich, K. J., Freres, D. R., Chaplin, T. M., Shatté, A. J., Samuels, B., et al. (2007). School-based prevention of depressive symptoms: A randomized controlled study of the effectiveness and specificity of the penn resiliency program. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 75(1), pp. 9–19. <https://doi.apa.org/doiLanding?doi=10.1037%2F0022-006X.75.1.9> (Accessed: December, 2021)
- Hart, A., & Heaver, B. (2015). Resilience Approaches to Supporting Young People’s Mental Health: Appraising the Evidence Base for Schools and Communities. Brighton: University of Brighton/ Boingboing.
- Rutter, M. (2007). Resilience, competence, and coping. *Child abuse and neglect*, pp. 205-209.